

Life World in Teaching among Maritime Instructors

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Abstract. This qualitative study explored the teaching-learning experiences of maritime instructors at the University of Cebu, aiming to understand their experiences, challenges, and aspirations to enhance training and development programs. Specifically, it examined positive and negative teaching experiences, strategies to address challenges, and instructors' aspirations to improve teaching performance. The study involved 20 maritime instructors, 10 from the marine transportation department and 10 from the marine engineering department, from the University of Cebu Maritime Education and Training Center and the University of Cebu Lapu-Lapu and Mandaue. Participants were selected using inclusion criteria. Data were gathered through a validated researcher-made questionnaire consisting of informants' profiles and open-ended questions. A transcendental phenomenological approach was employed to generate in-depth qualitative data. Seventeen (17) themes emerged. For teaching experiences, three (3) positive themes were identified: job satisfaction of former seafarers, building relationships with students, and improving oneself while working as a teacher. Seven (7) negative themes emerged: additional non-teaching responsibilities, insufficient training and orientation, time constraints to cover course contents, inadequate instructional materials, non-conducive learning environment, challenging students' attitude, and non-competitive teachers' salaries. In addressing challenges, four (4) themes surfaced: employ varied teaching-learning strategies, seek assistance from colleagues, listen to students' needs, and maintain a positive attitude. Lastly, two (2) aspiration themes emerged: pursue professional growth and development and receive regular feedback on teaching performance. Findings suggest that maritime higher education institutions should reevaluate training and seminar programs, emphasizing both simulator training and effective teaching strategies.

Introduction

The global demand of seafarers is growing year by year. The worldwide population of seafarers serving on internationally trading merchant ships is estimated at 1,647,500 seafarers, of which 774,000 are officers and 873,500 are ratings ([ics-shipping.org](https://www.ics-shipping.org)). Furthermore, according to the analysis conducted by United Nations Conference on Trade and Development [UNCTAD] (2018), world seaborne trade has gathered momentum and reached 10.7 billion tons per annum, with an annual growth rate of 4%.

Maritime Education in universities and colleges as the fundamental training ground (both theory and practice) for maritime students should make sure that they produce knowledgeable and skilled seafarers every school year. The instructor plays a key role in education, providing reinforcement and expert knowledge to facilitate students and their specific needs throughout the teaching process. During traditional maritime simulator training, the instructor and student interact collaboratively and continuously throughout a simulated scenario (Sellberg & Lundin, 2018).

As part of the stakeholders of schools, instructors play a very big role of the academic advancement and training of the maritime students. They are the ones who provide basic knowledge in seafaring. Over 40% of all cases of human errors on vessels were caused by an inadequate level of training, practical skills, and education of human resources. This paper represents an overview of research evaluating a virtual reality (VR) practical training course. The lack of human resources

in the maritime labor market causes a rapid promotion of maritime professionals, which in turn reduces the time to acquire required skills (Miyusov et al., 2022c). Maritime Education Institute should prepare the teachers and the students not just for today but also for future requirements. It requires them to understand the effect of digitalization on industry and adopt new programs as well as benefits from IT technology to improve their teaching and learning methods.

It is necessary to establish close cooperation and collaboration between industry and education institutes, and evaluate the missing points in the education system. A teaching system is required to enhance the ability to learners to use information and understand the importance of training and skills for their future. Traditionally, instructors dwell on lecture methods during the class discussion, but since the 1990's seafaring officer training has been reshaped to cover academic competencies to breed officers endowed with the ability to use highly improved technology.

As the Maritime Assessment Coordinator of the University of Cebu, the researcher saw the struggles of some instructors in preparing the daily lesson plan and the learning materials that are appropriate to use in the teaching- learning process. If the instructor does not have the plan of the day, a possible teaching strategy or delivery of the course can be difficult to organize in the entire hour of class instruction. There is very little research on the experiences of these instructors who are "masters" on board yet having difficulties in imparting knowledge and experiences on board to the future seafarers. Their job is to mold future captains and chief engineers on board, and because of that, they have to be well-equipped with the different strategies in developing lesson plans, delivering the course, and the different teaching methods that the pure teachers are learning.

In this premise, the researcher gathered the experiences of the maritime instructors in the University of Cebu Maritime Education Department, specifically the Maritime Training Center and University of Cebu Lapu-Lapu and Mandaue Campus. The researcher gathered teaching experiences, particularly in course delivery, lesson planning and teaching strategies in teaching professional subjects in the Maritime Department in Academic year 2022-2023.

Theoretical Background

This study is anchored on the Pragmatism Theory by John Dewey (1986) and is supported by Constructivism Theory by Jean Piaget (1964) and the Experiential Learning Theory by David Kolb (1984).

The theory of Pragmatism states that in education, there should be practical lessons that have value to the lives of learners in order to learn and be skilled. A pragmatic classroom involves project-based learning, play-based learning, experimentation, and experiential learning, which is what the mariners need in their classes.

According to the main theorist, John Dewey, Pragmatism, which he called "instrumentalism," is the view that knowledge results from the discernment of correlations between events, or processes of change. Inquiry requires active participation in such processes: the inquirer introduces specific variations in them to determine what differences thereby occur in related processes and measures how a given event changes in relation to variations in associated events. For example, experimental inquiry may seek to discern how malignancies in a human organism change in relation to variations in specific forms of treatment, or how students become better learners when exposed to particular methods of instruction (Gouinlock, 2024). True to the name he gave it, and in keeping with earlier pragmatists, Dewey held that ideas are instruments, or tools, that humans use to make greater sense of the world. Specifically, ideas are plans of action and predictors of future events. People possess an idea when they are prepared to use a given object in a manner that will produce a predictable result. Thus, people have an idea of a hammer when they are prepared to use such an object to drive nails into wood. Ideas predict that the undertaking of a definite line of conduct in specified conditions will produce a determinate result. Of course, ideas might be mistaken. They must be tested experimentally to see whether their predictions are borne out. Experimentation itself is fallible, but the chance for error is mitigated by further, more rigorous inquiry. Instrumentalism's operating premise is that ideas empower people to direct natural events, including social processes and institutions, toward human benefit (Gouinlock, 2024).

In addition, according to Sharma et al.(2018), there are four principles that teachers should know: utility, interest, experience, and integration. 1.) principle of utility explains that everything that students learn should have 'utility', which means that everything should be useful to the student.

A student doesn't care for learning abstract theoretical ideas that they will never apply to their lives outside of school. Instead, a student wants to learn things that are relevant to their lives. By making things relevant and useful, students will be more engaged and eager to learn; 2.) principle of Interest, which states that the curriculum content should also include the students' interests. Students have four interests: conversation, investigation, construction, and creative expression.

Therefore, teachers should focus on creating lessons that involve talking with one another, investigating things through experimentation, making things, and being creative; 3.) principle of experience, which elaborates that pragmatists value experience over all else. Students can learn abstract things all day, but unless they experience those things, they may never truly learn. Teachers should therefore create a lot of project-based, experimental, and experiential lessons that help children 'learn by doing'; and 4.) the principle of integration discusses that curriculum content is not separate.

Mathematics, Science, and Creative Arts are not three different lessons. Instead, the pragmatic teacher links the curriculum content together through a process we call 'integration'. The teacher will show students how concepts from different subjects are related to each other and encourage a holistic understanding of the topics they are learning (Sharma et al, 2018).

In conclusion, a pragmatic teacher uses active project-based learning strategies in the classroom and focuses on topics relevant to students' lives (Drew, 2022).

This study is also supported by Jean Piaget's Theory of Constructivism. According to Piaget (1964), learning is modeling, transforming, and understanding the way in which an object is constructed. Through interactions with the environment, we change our internalized view of the world. Views on separate constructs can be changed in different ways. Instead of there being a stimulus and then a response as a means of learning, Piaget (1964) proposed that there is actually a circular relationship between the two; a stimulus can cause a response, and that response can affect the way in which the next stimulus is viewed.

One's cognitive schema, or the way one thinks of a topic or object, is updated by external stimuli. Schemas can be adapted to the stimuli by either assimilation or accommodation. Assimilation takes new information from the environment and fits it with the pre-existing schema, whereas accommodation is the process of changing cognitive schemas in order to accept something new from the environment. Both of these processes can be used simultaneously and alternately throughout life. Constructivism equates learning with meaning that is created via experience; the mind filters input from the world to produce its own unique reality (Jonassen, 1991). Thus, humans learn by internally constructing meaning as opposed to acquiring it.

As people learn, they continually build personal interpretations of the world from input by experiences and interactions. The internal representation of one's knowledge is constantly open to change, and there is no objective reality that learners are to know and can eventually achieve. In order to understand the learning that has taken place for an individual, their experiences and how they experienced them must be examined.

In addition, Schunk (1991) reflected on a few questions that can be applied to the constructivist theory of learning: how does learning occur? Which factors influence learning? What is the role of memory in this learning theory? What types of learning are best explained by the theory? The same set of questions a 21st-century teacher should ask themselves. Another theory that supports this study is the Experiential Learning Theory. Experiential Learning Theory (ELT) emphasizes the importance of experience and its role in the learning process (Kolb, 1984). Kolb (1984) attests that, "learning is the process whereby knowledge is created through the transformation of experience."

Experiential Learning has four stages according to David Kolb (1984), which are concrete experience, reflective observation, abstract conceptualization, and active experimentation (Kurt, 2022). Kolb's learning process cycle begins with a concrete experience. This can either be a completely new experience or a reimagined experience that already happened. In a concrete experience, each learner engages in an activity or task. Kolb believed that the key to learning is involvement. It is not enough for learners to just read about it or watch it in action.

In order to acquire new knowledge, learners must actively engage in the task. After engaging in the concrete experience, the learner steps back to reflect on the task. This stage in the learning cycle allows the learner to ask questions and discuss the experience with others. Communication at this stage is vital, as it allows the learner to identify any discrepancies between their understanding and the experience itself. Good vocabulary also allows a solid review of the events that occurred.

The next step in the learning cycle is to make sense of these events. The learner attempts to draw conclusions of the experience by reflecting on their prior knowledge, using ideas with which they are familiar or discussing possible theories with peers. The learner moves from reflective observation to abstract conceptualization when they begin to classify concepts and form conclusions on the events that occurred. This involves interpreting the experience and making comparisons to their current understanding of the concept. Concepts need not be "new"; learners can analyse new information and modify their conclusions on already existing ideas. The last stage is the testing stage. Learners return to participating in a task, this time to apply their conclusions to new experiences. They are able to make predictions, analyse

tasks, and make plans for the acquired knowledge in the future. By allowing learners to put their knowledge into practice and showing how it is relevant to their lives, you are ensuring that the information is retained in the future.

Kolb's learning styles make up a holistic learning process. First, Diverging (Concrete Experience/Reflective Observation). This learning style takes an original and creative approach. Rather than examining concrete experiences by the actions taken, individuals tend to assess them from various perspectives. They value feelings and take an interest in others. Individuals who prefer this learning style tend to enjoy tasks such as brainstorming ideas and working collaboratively in groups. Second, Assimilating (Abstract Conceptualization/Reflective Observation).

This learning style emphasizes reasoning. Individuals who demonstrate this learning style can review the facts and assess the experience. They tend to enjoy designing experiments and working on projects from start to completion. Third, Converging (Abstract Conceptualization/ Active Experimentation). This learning style highlights problem-solving as an approach to learning. Individuals who prefer this learning style can make decisions and apply their ideas to new experiences. Unlike Divergers, they tend to avoid people and perceptions, choosing instead to find technical solutions.

Fourth, Accommodating (Concrete Experience Active Experimentation). This learning style is adaptable and intuitive. These individuals use trial and error to guide their experiences, preferring to discover the answers for themselves. They can alter their path based on the circumstance and generally have good people skills (Kurt, 2022).

In a clearer context, learning is a concrete experience as it is the way the students perceive the real world. It could be from drawing the different parts of a ship to riding in a real ship or a virtual reality experience inside a ship; and from looking at a picture of the machinery on board the vessel to immersing in a shipboard training. There is more to what is written and what is seen in a book for a student to learn and familiarize the skills that are taught in school. Training, immersions, simulation, and virtual reality are a few of the innovations in schools that can help the teaching and learning experience be successful. There are several skill-based trainings that the Maritime Industry requires to the seafarers before embarkation or promotion. The same is true when they are still in their undergraduate studies.

The Maritime Industry continues to move the trades around the world with the help of the International Maritime Organization to develop skilled maritime seafarers. The Philippines, as one of the top producers of maritime graduates, strives to engage its schools in training programs to be able to pass the standard and to maintain its name at the top of the list. The school, as the foundation of learning of our seafarers, are in constant need of support and fast-track improvement to cope with the innovations of technology in the Maritime Industry. With that, our teachers as the primary source of knowledge, need to be updated on what technology to use and new teaching strategies to produce quality graduates who will soon be masters and chief engineers of the vessels they will be serving.

In a study conducted by Manuel (2017), it interestingly investigated the comparison of having maritime courses as vocational and academic. Manuel stated that it must be emphasized that the reference to education is not just to the status quo of education but to a paradigm of education that recognizes the inherent worth of individuals and enables them to develop in a way that gives full expression to their potential.

The Standards of Training, Certification and Watch-keeping (STCW) Code states that every person conducting in-service training the assessment of competence of providing training and assessment within an institution shall: have a full understanding of the specific objectives of the particular training being conducted and have knowledge and understanding of the competence to be assessed; be qualified in the task for which the training is to be conducted; in the instance of simulator training, every instructor shall receive appropriate guidance in instructional techniques and gain practical operational experience on the particular type of simulators used.

According to the recommendations of Section B-I/6 of the STCW Convention (which is currently non-mandatory) any person, supervisor or assessor on-board or ashore, conducting in-service training of a seafarer intended to be used in qualifying for certification, should have received appropriate guidance in instructional techniques and assessment methods using relevant IMO Model Courses; appropriate guidance in assessment methods and practice; gained practical assessment experience under the supervision of an experienced assessor; for those individuals responsible for supervising in-service training, should have appropriate knowledge of instructional techniques, training methods and practices.

The instructor should be familiar with teaching strategies and should be able to select appropriate teaching skills for a certain group of trainees. Teaching should be diverse and interesting, and trainees should be able to understand the concept of the training programme. Instructors should continuously check and assess the motivation and the trainees. Sometimes, when the instructor has been teaching for a long time, he is no longer focused on motivating students to learn but rather on delivering the content, which can be very teacher-centered and boring to some of the learners. Experience shows that an unmotivated group usually consists of over-experienced or over-confident mariners.

To align maritime programs with the needs of maritime stakeholders, their curriculum should inscribe business and management skills, e.g., language, decision making, leadership, organizational knowledge, interpersonal, etc., into consideration (Lau & Ng, 2015). Indeed, they should equip students with the desired skills and proper knowledge, and professional attitudes for the maritime industry. Although the demands for both under- and postgraduate maritime studies programs keep growing rapidly, the reasons for such demand remain rather unclear.

Maritime instructors should have all necessary teaching competencies and be aware of all topics required by STCW. They should also be cognizant of human elements and potential issues experienced by trainees that can affect the teaching progress. Awareness of the factors that could influence teaching and spill over into the behavior of both the trainees and instructors is of utmost importance for adequate transfer of knowledge (Kalulu, 2018). The following are factors that influence teaching: motivation, ability to self-motivate and motivate others (Tang & Sampson, 2017); instruction techniques and teaching methods, accessibility to a conducive; learning environment and teaching aids and ability to devise an appropriate; training programme for delivery (Justice et al., 2007); communication, ability to effectively monitor and communicate; (behavior analysis) with their students; appropriate experience, having marine background and holding STCW; certificates. When all these factors are present in class, the teaching and learning process is successful.

Along with the factors are challenges that an instructor will face during the teaching and learning process. One of those is the delivery of the course; as they are not pure educators, there is a tendency that they will have a hard time managing the classroom. Mariners are skilled workers shaped to maneuver the ship, troubleshoot the machinery in the engine room, and maintain the vessel to sail safely and transport from one port to another; hence, they are not trained intensively to teach in a classroom. When a teacher comes into the classroom, the students are expected to learn something; however, if the teacher comes in ready with only his discussion and sharing of experiences on board the vessel, there could be a problem of retaining the attention of the students until the end of the discussion. As practiced by "TED talk,"; each speaker is allotted only 18 minutes per speaker as it is believed that a person's attention span and interest last only 18 minutes.

The academic literature is replete with articles and books supporting and propagating the conclusion that lectures should adhere to the 10- to 15-minute attention span that is characteristic of modern students. When the lecture begins, most students are paying attention, and for most students, that attention lasts for about 10 minutes. When there are no other activities other than lecture or discussion, it might be difficult to get a hold of the students' attention and retention. In the teaching profession, it is important to note that the students must be involved in the teaching and learning process; they must actively participate in the discussion.

Furthermore, when a lesson plan is set to engage the interest of the students through a springboard, motivate the students in learning through a short video clip or a game, start the discussion with a clear picture of what to expect at the end of the class, and assess the students learning before concluding the class time, it might be that the instructors can successfully deliver the intended learning outcome of the day. However, if not, then there must be an intervention of what went wrong in the entire process. Student engagement in the discussion is very important in retention of what is expected to learn, as the students are to express their understanding and share their ideas and opinions about the topics discussed.

With the aforementioned factors that influence the teaching process, it can be concluded that a lot can be extracted from the experiences of the Maritime Instructors since the pandemic has continued making transitions in the educational system, and at the same time, instructors are still coping with the change of their career path, which is from seafaring to teaching. Not all instructors are teachers, but all of them should be qualified to teach. The Official Gazette of The Republic of Croatia (No. 130/13), which regulates qualifications, educational requirements, examination programme, qualification programme, conditions and ways of obtaining certificates and additional qualifications for the master, chief engineer, chief mates and other crew members of seagoing vessels. Besides the aforementioned, the code also regulates the following: conditions which must be fulfilled by the universities and high schools which educate candidates for certificates for qualification; conditions which must be fulfilled by the examiners and members of the examination committees; procedures and the way of issuing the approval to the institutions which organize seafarers' qualifications, procedures and ways of issuing certificates for qualified seafarers education. The code has been compiled in accordance with certain EU Directives (Učur, 2014). Part G1 of the code covers basic requirements and part G2 covers specific requirements including quality standards, technical requirements for instructors and educational programs. When concerning teaching staff every teacher or instructor should have: sufficient sea-experience and knowledge in the relevant subject, knowledge of the entire programme of education/training in which the teacher participates, knowledge of the specific objectives of the relevant education or training, knowledge of relevant teaching methods, their application and effects, a conscientious and consistently adaptable approach to incorporating technological and other changes in shipping into teaching activities and an ability to evaluate and favorably shape the professional and human personalities of the participants, as future seamen. As one of the largest maritime suppliers of seafarers worldwide, the Philippines must set high standards for all maritime industry stakeholders, maritime training institutions, assessment centers, instructors, assessors, supervisors, and other entities and individuals concerned. On the other hand, simulator-based training is also a cost-effective and powerful

solution that allows instructors to create diverse and replaceable scenarios, which they would not otherwise be able to train due to safety, economic, and ethical constraints of real-life training exercises (Lundh et al., 2012).

It takes a lot of effort to become a seafarer, same goes for being a teacher in a maritime institution. Since maritime students need caliber instructors, they are to be trained to teach and trained to assess. As discussed in the first few paragraphs of this section, an instructor must be equipped with at least 3 major training courses of the maritime course: the 6.09 IMO course, the 3.12 IMO course, and the 6.10 Assessor's Course. IMO Model Courses are designed to help implement the STCW Convention and, further, to facilitate access to the knowledge and skills demanded by increasingly sophisticated maritime technology. Maritime institutes and their teaching staff can use them in organizing and introducing new courses or in enhancing, updating, or supplementing existing training material.

Another factor that influences the teaching process is the change in the learning environment. Since the pandemic, the teaching and learning process has been topsy-turvy. There were a lot of adaptations, adjustments, challenges, and changes in the education sector in all countries worldwide. In a study conducted in Saudi Arabia, the results showed that the online modality was well-received, and all participants agreed that online sessions were time saving and that their performance was improved due to enhance utility of time; however, they indicated that they encountered some challenges, including methodological, content perception, technical, and behavioral challenges during session and online exams (Khalil et al. 2020).

In a study conducted by Abante et al. (2021), it was revealed that each sector has a problem with internet connectivity. Specifically, public school teachers are being challenged by the scarce resources of the students and unresponsive parents. Private school teachers are being challenged by the lack of training on the different online platforms for the online teaching and learning process and assessment of learning. Instructors play a very important role in the teaching and learning process. When the instructor is not on top of the preparation of the cadets, the quality of the graduates in schools could be below the standard of the CHED Marina or even European accrediting bodies.

Other than the learning environment, the well-being of the teachers plays an important role in the teaching-learning process. According to Roelen et al. (2008), there are seven key indicators of job satisfaction: task variety; colleagues; working conditions; workload; autonomy; education and development opportunities; and person-environment fit. Task Variety is the amount of variation one perceives to have in his or her role; colleagues, on the other hand is how happy one is with his or her coworkers; working condition is the physical conditions of the workplace (e.g., orderliness, cleanliness, a reasonable commute, etc.) and the ethos of the organizations (e.g. promoting creativity and collaboration). Moreover, workload is the amount of work one must do (i.e., not too little and not too much). Autonomy is the amount of control one feels over his or her position (e.g., flexible working and being able to manage work around other commitments), while education and development opportunities are the amount of growth and learning an employee can do. Finally, the person's environment fit is the match between an individual and his or her work environment. It takes courage, patience, and perseverance to be an educator. There are so many tasks to do, before, during, and after getting into a class; from the preparation of the lesson plans, instructional materials, mastery of the lessons, to conducting the class and checking the assessments right after. Teaching is a very challenging job, and it requires your time and effort to successfully transfer your knowledge and skills to the learners, which seafarers are not used to doing.

Koh (2021) found that there is a six-factor solution that confirms the proposed quality dimensions of the exploratory analysis. The following quality dimensions have the most impact on student satisfaction (1) technology integration, followed by (2) industrial exposure, (3) learning and teaching environment, (4) industry-aligned & innovative curriculum, (5) faculty member competencies, and finally (6) supporting activities. In addition, student satisfaction positively influences engagement and academic performance. Minimizing gaps between theory and practice is the aim of the instructors for the whole semester. If the students fail in their practical examination, then there must be something wrong with the way they discuss the theories prior to the assessment.

In the study conducted by Jamil & Bhuiyan (2021), the result stated that there is a need to define clear learning outcomes, improve learning content to enable exploration and second chance learning, minimize theory- practice gaps by ensuring skills-knowledge balance and in depth scholarship building facilitating tasks for learning preparation and learning extension, and repositioning simulation components and their assessment schemes across pandemic programme. In terms of maritime simulation by using the latest and most advanced simulators, there is a chance that the students can practically learn from experiencing the real scenarios on board and explore the knowledge and skills provided by the maritime schools. Gaps can be less or close when schools are engaging the students in practical examinations more than the written or theoretical. To support this claim, experience is really what matters in acquiring aesthetic skills in the maritime industry. As Naval Architecture students were being studied in Australia by Abeywardhan et al. (2017), the findings prove that experiential learning is a "paradigm of noteworthy learning" that supports multiple learning objectives of learners and shapes their knowledge through experience. While on board, cadets are assessed on 143 STCW competencies from the

OICNW, able seafarer deck and ratings forming a part of the navigation watch tables. The remaining STCW competencies are assessed ashore, in the classroom, laboratories, simulators, or aboard the maritime academy's small vessels. There are a lot of instructional materials and assessment tools in the maritime industry that keep on improving and evolving from time to time due to the demand of the job.

Moreover, in the study of Mallam et al. (2019), virtual reality, augmented reality, and mixed reality are technologies that provide new possibilities and methods during planned and unplanned work, command and control, scenario testing, communication, and knowledge exchange between crew, ships, and ship-to-shore networks. However, as with the new technology, especially as captivating as VR, AR, and MR, many issues need to be addressed and investigated to better understand their strengths and limitations.

Johnson (2020) found out that the imperative evolution in response to change is equally truism for the business of shipping (to include the merchant marine industry, cruise tourism, and hospitality) as it is for the business of higher education (HE), especially MET. Moreover, MET focuses on the equipping of the human element in shipping, and it is the engine behind a multi-billion-dollar industry that is driven by global trade, which is facilitated by ships and ports. With this innovation, market needs for skills will shift from the able-bodied seafarer to a robust knowledge base in cyber-physical systems (CPSs). This reality will necessitate change in instruction, curriculum planning, and outcomes in MET.

In another aspect, a study conducted by Manuel (2017), interestingly looked into the comparison of having maritime courses as vocational and academic. It was stated that it must be emphasized that the reference to education is not just to the status quo of education but to a paradigm of education that recognizes the inherent worth of individuals and enables them to develop in a way that gives full expression to their potential. Furthermore, it is recognized that there will be different levels of education and training for support, operational, and management levels of competency (per the requirements of the STCW Convention). Incorporating academic requirements for the different levels will certainly require different approaches.

The attributed theories, related literature and studies herein defined and explained the lived experiences of a former seafarer- now a teacher in the Maritime Education.

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to explore the life-world experiences in teaching among Maritime instructors at the University of Cebu.

Specifically, it aimed to answer the following questions:

What are the experiences in teaching maritime among the informants?

How do the informants address the challenges encountered in teaching maritime programs?

What are the aspirations of the informants to improve their teaching performance?

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized the qualitative transcendental phenomenological design to explore the experiences of the maritime instructors in their course delivery, lesson planning and teaching strategies in the maritime department. Transcendental phenomenology (TPh), largely developed by Husserl, is a philosophical approach to qualitative research methodology seeking to understand human experience (Moustakas, 1994). Pure TPh is grounded in the concept and conditioned upon setting aside all preconceived ideas (epoche) to see phenomena through unclouded glasses, thereby allowing the true meaning of phenomena to naturally emerge with and within their own identity (Moustakas, 1994).

Research Participants

The research informants of this study are 5 instructors per program and per institution who are teaching professional or technical subjects in the maritime department for at least 2 semesters within the academic year 2021- 2022 and 2022-2023. They are seasoned seafarers who took their time to gain certifications in 6.09 (teaching methodologies) training and 3.12 (assessment learning) before they applied and got hired in the university as instructors. The informants were chosen using purposive sampling. The researcher employed data saturation, where if no data is generated, this is a signal to stop collecting any additional new data.

Research Environment

The study was conducted at the University of Cebu Maritime Education. UC - Maritime Education and Training Center (METC) and UC Lapu-Lapu and Mandaue both offer future seafarers thorough teaching and training, complete with technological simulators, while accredited with and abiding by international standards set by the DNV-ISO, Panama Maritime Authority, and the Norwegian Liberian Maritime Authority. METC is the preferred source for recruitment by 40 international and local shipping companies and other manning agencies.

In May 1995, the University of Cebu Lapu-Lapu and Mandaue rose up in the foot of Mactan and Mandaue Bridge. In UCLM, a scholarship is offered to students who dream of being world-class seafarers, the NSA. The Norwegian Shipowners Association is a model for assimilation and loyalty to the company culture even before going on board. Aside from company-sponsored funding for tuition and lodging, NSA scholars are assured a spot on board their vessels plying international routes. There are a total of 60 marine transportation instructors and 43 marine engineering instructors for the whole Maritime Education Program. The UC Maritime Education is equipped with Engine Room Simulators, Electronic Chart Display and Information System, Liquid Cargo Handling Simulator, Automatic Radar Plotting Aid, Full Mission Simulator and other machinery in the machine shop.

Research Instrument

Although the researcher was the primary instrument of this qualitative study, a researcher-made interview questionnaire will be used to gather valuable data (Please refer to *Appendix B* for the interview guide). The interview guide contains series of guide questions that helped extract the desired answers from the informants. The research instrument was verified by experts to establish the validity of its content.

Research Procedure

Data Collection

After the approval of the transmittal letter to the Maritime Superintendent and the Dean of the Maritime Department, the ethics reviewer, and the validation of the questionnaire from the experts, the researcher interviewed in the most convenient time and place of the maritime instructors. The informed consent was discussed and given to the instructor before asking interview guide questions.

The data collection was recorded and was written to ensure the completeness and correctness of data, with the approval of the informants. When some of the instructors refused to be interviewed personally, an option for a virtual interview was provided. Aside from that, when some of the instructors were not available, an interview guide questionnaire was given. After the interview, the researcher ensured that all data gathered was kept confidential and that the results would also be shared with them if they asked for it.

Data Analysis

First, the research recorded the answers of the informants and encoded them verbatim; some instructors who were not available for a face-to-face interview were given an option to have it in a virtual interview, or they could be given an interview set of questions on paper so they could answer it during their free time. After acquiring the data, the researcher determined the themes and analyzed each. Finally, the researcher uses ethical principles in research in the conduct of the study.

Ethical Consideration

The principles used were beneficence, confidentiality, and informed consent.

The researcher makes sure the informants are treated in an ethical manner, not only by respecting their decisions and protecting them from harm, but also by making efforts to secure their well-being.

The research makes sure that respect to human rights (for example, privacy of patients' personal information) is prioritized. The research study should maximize the benefits for both parties while minimizing any possible harm. Special care should be taken when working with vulnerable groups, like, children, people with disability, and older people. Any sensitive information that is provided in confidence, including diagnostic results, grants information, patients' records, etc., should be protected (Resnick, 2015).

The researcher respects the rank of the instructor being interviewed, because these instructors were once captains, 2nd mates, 1st mates, or officials on board and they may be strong when it comes to expressing their feelings in the challenges that they have encountered in the academe, especially in the preparation or lesson plans or content delivery; the researcher should understand, pay respect and prevents anything that may cause dismay to the informants. Since the research can focus more on the maritime instructors' performance in the academe, the researcher will assure the informants that their answers are confidential and that without their authorization, they will not be exposed to anyone.

The researcher will never force the informants to participate, nor use their names for the data that were not theirs. All informants must give their permission to be part of the study, and they must be given pertinent information to make an "informed" consent to participate.

Trustworthiness of Research

The rigor of a study refers to the degree of confidence in data, interpretation, and methods used to ensure the quality of a study (Polit & Beck, 2014). The researcher has consulted professional researchers and professors on the conduct of the research to ensure that the tools to be used to gather pertinent data are valid.

Credibility. The confidence in the truth of the study and therefore the findings is the most important criterion (Polit & Beck, 2014). Techniques used to establish credibility include prolonged engagement with the participants, persistent observation if appropriate to the study, peer-debriefing, member-checking, and reflective journaling. Evidence should also be presented of iterative questioning of the data, returning to examine it several times. Since the study will be conducted in the University where the researcher works, it is easier for the researcher to communicate and meet the informants from time to time. If there is a need for the researcher to observe the classes, then it will be processed accordingly.

Dependability. Refers to the stability of the data over time and over the conditions of the study (Polit & Beck, 2014). As mentioned in the credibility, the researcher is working together with the informants in the same University. In this premise, the data can be gathered without time and distance constraints, hence if there is data needed for the fullness of the research.

Confirmability. It is the neutrality, or the degree findings are consistent and could be repeated. Methods include maintenance of an audit trail of analysis and methodological memos of log (Polit & Beck, 2014). The study, which involves instructors, can be used for the next years to come with different sets of instructors and different curricula. In this way, the research confirmability is justified. For now, this research is using the same set of instructors; all marine transportation and all marine engineering teaching in the same year, and the same curriculum is used.

Transferability. The extent to which findings are useful to persons in other settings is different from other aspects of research in that readers determine how applicable the findings are to their situations. This study can be used in different MHEIs around the Philippines, since the same curriculum applies to all Maritime schools in the Philippines, and therefore the same set of standards.

Results and Discussion

This qualitative study used a thorough understanding of the transcribed responses (please refer to Appendix E for the verification form of the transcription) of each of the key informants by reading and re-reading the transcripts to determine the general sense of the whole coverage of the content. The significant statements from the interview guide questions were extracted and read carefully to properly code the data. There were a total of 20 informants from the maritime department in both the University of Cebu Lapu-Lapu and Mandaue and the University of Cebu Mambaling Campus who were teaching for more than 3 years in the Maritime Department.

The following were the emergent themes and the clustered themes:

I. Experiences in Teaching Maritime Among Informants In Teaching Maritime Programs

A. Positive Experiences

1. Job Satisfaction of Former Seafarers
2. Building Relationships with Students
3. Improving One's Self while Working as a Teacher

B. Negative Experiences

1. Additional Non-Teaching Responsibilities
2. Insufficient Training and Orientation

3. Time Constraints to Cover Course Contents
4. Inadequate Instructional Materials
5. Non-Conducive Learning Environment
6. Challenging Students' Attitude
7. Non-Competitive Teacher's Salary

II. Addressing the Challenges Encountered by the Informants in Teaching Maritime Programs

1. Employ Varied Teaching-Learning Strategies
2. Seek Assistance from Colleagues
3. Seek Assistance from Colleagues
4. Listen to the Students' Needs
5. Maintain a Positive Attitude

III. Aspirations of the Informants to Improve their Teaching Performance

1. Pursue Professional Growth and Development
2. Receive Regular Feedback on Teaching Performance

The themes that emerged in the study were carefully developed to explain the phenomenon using the narratives of the maritime instructors, both from UC-METC and UC-LM. The themes clearly answered the problem statement of the study.

The seventeen (17) emergent themes with their different clusters are as follows:

I. Experiences in Teaching Maritime Among Informants

A. Positive Experiences

1. Job Satisfaction of Former Seafarers. The first theme that emerged in the narratives of the seafarers has something to do with the satisfaction they experience in teaching that is different from the satisfaction they felt when they were still seafarers.

"Job security, flexible working schedule and a chance to make an impact to the community. Today's classrooms are engaging, lively environments where innovation is promoted. The most typical kind of flexible working arrangement offered to teachers is part-time work, which involves working fewer days or fewer hours each day. Although you can plan your work around your current duties, your income will be prorated to your working hours (IDI 11 -1B)."

2. Building Relationships with Students. This theme is derived based on the narratives of the informants on how their experiences are important in the learning of the future seafarers and their relationship with the students inside the four walls of the classroom.

"One of the greatest fulfilment of being a seafarer is the opportunity to share valuable experience through teaching (IDI 1-1B)."

3. Improving One's Self while Working as a Teacher. The theme was developed from the experiences of the two teachers who improved their skills through teaching. As a teacher, it is necessary to learn and re-learn from time to time to stay on track, to be updated with the latest curriculum, student (generation) behavior and others, especially the maritime teachers are not teachers by profession.

"Teaching maritime subjects often involves staying updated with the latest industry trends, regulations, and technologies. As an instructor, you'll develop strong communication, presentation, and interpersonal skills (IDI 9-1B)."

B. Negative Experiences

1. Additional Non-Teaching Responsibilities. This theme is derived from the narratives of the instructors who are burdened by tasks that are outside the teaching and learning process. For the teachers to focus on their classes, they must not be bombarded with extracurricular:

"There are times when the situation calls for full cooperation of instructors particularly during audits. Various paper works have to be complied for us to pass and succeed with fewer observations. Preparation for the MARINA and EMSA Audit was one of the most exhausting time and I could say though it may be tiring but it gave me an edge and necessary experience in audit preparations. A lot of overtime and working hour extension were done just to make things ready (IDI 1-1 D)."

2. Insufficient Training and Orientation. The theme generated from the orientation of the teaching strategies, methodologies, and others related to the teaching profession due to a lack of personnel in the department and a large number of enrollees and seafarers' sudden decision to go on board in the middle of the enrollment process.

"No proper orientation during my first months as an instructor. Not enough developmental training before the job (IDI 2-1D)."

3. Time Constraints to Cover Course Contents. This theme was derived from the narratives of the teachers regarding the numerous topics that are impossible to deliver at a given time. The idealism that goes with the curriculum is not new in Maritime Education.

"The pressure, so many classes yet so little time to cover all the topics (IDI 10-1D)."

4. Inadequate Instructional Materials. This theme is derived from the narratives of the teachers regarding the textbooks that are outdated, or the ability to provide supplements to the discussion. The course packages or course syllabus do not come with books and hyperlinks to be used for discussion; hence, maritime teachers have to resort to different books or articles to read to utilize during classroom discussion.

"We had books before but they outdated. We have online books now and internet so we rely on them but we are not the same (IDI 3-1D)."

5. Non-Conducive Learning Environment. A theme that is derived from the teacher's experience of classrooms that are not conducive to the teaching and learning process. The classrooms of the University are not air-conditioned and are near big establishments with trucks passing by the campus, which would cause too much noise.

"Large class sizes can make it challenging to provide personalized attention to each student. As a Maritime Instructor, you might find it difficult to interact with every student in the depth required for effective learning. This can lead to students feeling overlooked or struggling to ask questions (IDI 19-1D)."

6. Challenging Students' Attitude. This theme was derived from the teachers' sentiments on the teachers on the students' challenging behavior, attitude towards learning, treatment of their teachers, and classmates.

"First is the type of students. Some are really hard headed and not interested to learn. They are just there and that is all. Second is the preparation of the materials to teach, it is not easy since I am not a teacher and the training I had was a short one. So I have to ask to the Gen Ed instructors on how to do it (IDI 10-1D)."

7. Non-Competitive Teacher's Salary. This theme was generated from the narratives of the instructors on the difference of their pay from being on board to teaching in the academe.

"One negative experience maybe is the huge difference between what I earn while on board and what I earn now in the academe (IDI 8-1D)."

II. Addressing the Challenges Encountered by the Informants in Teaching the Maritime Program

1. Employ Varied Teaching- Learning Strategies. This theme was derived from the narratives of the teachers in trying their best to cope up with all the challenges they experienced, especially not being an education graduate.

"Offering additional resources or support to students who need extra help to grasp concepts, and challenging advanced learners with more in-depth material. Overcoming this challenge "Large class sizes, making individual attention difficult" requires innovative strategies to maintain a productive."

2. Seek Assistance from Colleagues. The theme is generated through the narrative of the teachers who experienced attending various seminars or asking for the assistance of a General Education Teacher or Senior Colleagues who have been teaching for more than 5 years.

"I attend to trainings. Most of the time I watch videos and I discuss it with my colleagues (IDI-2-2B)."

3. Listen to the Students' Need. The theme is derived from the resolutions the teachers' thought about when they do not understand the behavior of their students or they are not sure if the students learned or not. Maritime teachers are not trained to handle students and to control their behavior unlike the regular teachers.

"One of my aspirations as an instructor is to have a more student- centered approach of teaching. I want to focus on the needs and learning styles of individual student and incorporate more interactive and collaboration activities into my lessons. I believe that providing more opportunities for students to ask questions and participant in discussions and lead to more engaging and effective learning experience (IDI 6-3B)."

4. Maintain a Positive Attitude. The theme that is derived when the maritime teacher is trying his best to understand the students at the same time helping them learn necessary things to prepare them on board.

"I just maintain a positive attitude and I just pray to God if ever I encounter challenges along the way (IDI 13-2B)."

III. Aspirations of the Informants to Improve Their Teaching Performance

1. Pursue Professional Growth and Development. This theme is derived from the narratives of the teachers who are pursuing post-degree units to improve and be more familiar with the teaching profession, especially those who do not have plans to go on board again.

"I am looking forward also to further my skills in the field of education such as engaging in Master's class or whenever time permits. Lastly, I would fill myself with the necessary knowledge as much as I could so I could be a more effective educator to my students (IDI 1-3B)."

2. Receive Regular Feedback on Teaching Performance. This theme is formed by a narrative of two of the teachers who believed that getting comments and suggestions from their students and fellow teachers helped them become better educators mentioned:

"I constantly strive to improve my teaching performance by seeking feedback from my students and peers. This feedback helps me identify areas of strength and weaknesses and provide opportunities for growth and development (IDI 7-3B)."

Analysis of Data

Moustaka's (1994) transcendental or psychological phenomenology focused less on the interpretations of the research and more on the description of the experiences of the participants. This case study presents everything that the maritime instructors have experienced in their teaching profession.

I. Experiences in Teaching Maritime Among the Informants

A. Positive Experience

1. Job Satisfaction of Former Seafarers. The seafarers are known to be working on board for 6-9 months or, in some cases, one year straight. They have a day off every Sunday if and only if there is no emergency on board. Based on the interview, the teachers are grateful to have a job even when they are on land with 2 days off and after work time for themselves and their family, unlike on board, and a source of income. Although some teachers are complaining about the compensation, others were just satisfied with having a job they can spend their time on when they are not working on board. They can share experiences and make acquaintances with other seafarers. According to Dobrow et al. (2018), with more than 21,000 participants in their study, they found that over 40 years, people who stayed in the same organization over time became less satisfied, and people who moved to different organizations over time became happier. Surprisingly, some of the instructors feel that they are happy and satisfied with the job they have, mentioning that, on board, they do now have vacation leave for straight 6-8 months, but in the teaching profession, you have the weekend for yourself and your family.

2. Building Relationship with Students. A teacher will always leave a mark on his or her students' lives, no matter what. The teachings, the bond they create together, and the impact of it on the daily lives of the students will have to do something in their future. The maritime teachers are not exempt from this fulfilling award. In the interview, seeing their students embark on or take on a new journey after graduating or even during their apprenticeship makes them very happy, knowing they contributed something to the students' future. Irrespective of their job titles or salary, employees who are more satisfied with their job, whether they feel satisfied with the organizational culture, with the rewards they are getting, or with recognition, can produce more and do it more efficiently (Gerhart, 1987). Teachers are the second parents of the students; seeing them succeed and achieve their goals in life is always a cause for a parent's smile. It is like a reward that is not expected but eventually comes without notice when teachers get surprises from their students before, and it will just melt their hearts.

3. Improving One's Self while Working as a Teacher. To be in an environment where you are not just working but also growing professionally as an individual is just reassuring. It's no surprise that once a culture is established in a workplace, satisfaction can then be enhanced by feelings of security. Security may arise from knowing you work for a viable company with long-term goals, insinuating feelings of belonging to that company (Berg et al., 2010). According to Roelen et al. (2008), one key indicator of job satisfaction is Education and Development opportunities, which are the amount of growth and learning an employee can do. Several maritime teachers are already working on their postgraduate studies to further improve their teaching skills and secure their position in the academe. While they are already veterans at their work as a seafarer, an additional skill gives a positive experience as a person. To them, they are learning and earning from it while they are not on board.

B. Negative Experiences

1. Additional Non-Teaching Responsibilities. This is the first sentiment of the maritime teachers in the University of Cebu. In some cases, teachers, whether new or old, are requested to help or assist in audits and verification of the accrediting body of the University. Other than being an additional task to the teacher, it is difficult for them especially to the new teachers who are still in their familiarization phase in the academe or newbies. The teachers are to support the Curriculum Development Center in making course packages; from lesson plans, instructional materials and the assessment tools for the whole semester and help the department in all the objective evidence the school needs to present the accrediting body. According to Latham (2012), motivation is a cognitive resource allocation process in which a person makes choices as to the time and energy to be allocated to an array of motives or tasks. The keyword here seems to be choice. When an employee

can make a choice, they feel more motivated to perform a task. When an employee is more motivated to perform and complete a task, this tends to be linked with higher job satisfaction (Jalagat, 2016). However, in the maritime department, there is a very limited choice since the manpower is not sufficient. The course packages need to be developed by professional teachers only because they are very technical, so the teachers need to successfully pass the audit.

2. **Insufficient Training and Orientation.** As part of the stakeholders of schools, instructors play a very big role in the academic advancement and training of the maritime students. Hence, the teachers should have constant review and training on these new simulators at the same time, on how to teach them to the students to achieve quality learning. The existing problem in the maritime department is that the instructors do not really use the simulators, especially the older ones. The reason for this is that they are not very familiar with the simulators, and it is very alarming since the students need to be assessed. This is the reason why, during the interview, many of the teachers said they need more training and seminars related to teaching and simulator utilization. In traditional maritime simulator training, the instructor and student interact collaboratively and continuously throughout a simulated scenario (Sellberg, 2018).

3. **Time Constraints to Cover Course Contents.** As one of the course package developers, specifically the assessment part, there is really a glitch in the course topics and the time allotment of the curriculum. Jean Piaget (1964), where assimilation takes new information from the environment and fits it with the pre-existing scheme, there has to be an effort in exhausting the previous knowledge of the students to connect it with the new one, like review test, review discussion, video watching, and many more, which will take time to execute. Sometimes, in one learning outcome, there is 1 topic with 8 subtopics to be discussed in 3 hours. In this case, it is much better to discuss it than having additional activities that will take time, as a result, the time allotment for that certain topic will not be enough.

4. **Inadequate Instructional Materials.** Innovation with technology, Augmented Learning Platform, and other AIs are what are trending in the Maritime Industry; hence, the school or academe should start providing the teachers and students with all they need in the classroom that can supplement the discussion. Although the University of Cebu Maritime Program provides the necessary laboratory equipment, some is not updated. In the Theory of Constructivism, one of the principles is "learning is an active process," which explains that sensory input is used to construct meaning. They should be moving, exploring, and not just sitting and listening to the discussion of the teacher.

5. **Non-Conducive Learning Environment.** Being in the Maritime Academe and teaching part-time to maritime students as well, the researcher witnessed how the students are uncomfortable and irritable with their long sleeves on Wednesdays and uniform attire on the rest of the days due to the hot and humid weather of Cebu.

A healthy environment invites and prospers this interaction and learning. Most complaints from the teachers are about the ventilation of the classrooms, since both Maritime Campuses are near the sea, and the sea breeze can be hot and humid with their uniforms on. The large number of students in the classroom can be very uncomfortable for both teachers and students. In another scenario, the laboratories can only accommodate half of the class size, and so some of the students can be waiting outside until their turn to use the simulators or Progressive education recognizes that social interaction is a key to learning, and they use conversation, interaction, and group applications to help students retain their knowledge.

6. **Challenging Students' Attitude.** This theme is formed by a narrative of two of the teachers who believed that getting comments and suggestions from their students and fellow teachers helped them become better educators. In relation to the Experiential Learning Theory (ELT), it emphasizes the importance of experience and its role in the learning process (Kolb, 1984). The students need to do it, act on it, immerse themselves in the real scenario, to learn the process and to acknowledge the difference between what is written in theories and what is applied in practice. The students need to always be a part of the learning process, changing from being passive to active learners.

7. **Non-Competitive Teacher's Salary.** The Maritime Profession is giving them a salary that could range from 100,000-500,000 PHP, depending on the rank or position, and a teacher only receives from 20,000-50,000, depending on their degree and tenure. It can be a really big difference and a source of a challenge. Organizational success and job satisfaction are also linked to employees' perceptions of adequate pay and benefits (Edwards, 2008).

II. Addressing the Challenges Encountered by the Informants in Teaching Maritime Programs

1. **Employ Varied Teaching-Learning Strategies.** To overcome challenges, maritime teachers find ways to make teaching a stress-free job for themselves. There is no question as to "what" they can teach the students; the question here is the "how" they can transfer the knowledge to them, and if it is effective enough to say that it is a successful transfer of learning. Darling-Hammond (1997) mentioned that teaching matters and relationship matters. The teachers are skillful enough to provide their students with the best learning experience and at the same time a strong bond to create with the learners because most of their lessons are based on experience on board; the future they will anticipate through their teachers.

2. **Seek Assistance from Colleagues.** Rather than thinking of herself as weak because she asks for suggestions or help, a teacher views collaboration to learn from a fellow professional. A great teacher uses constructive criticism and advice as an opportunity to grow as an educator. A maritime teacher can opt to attend various training and seminars related to teaching and the recent innovations in the maritime industry as a refresher or to seek new knowledge or seek. Darling-Hammond (1997) said that teaching matters and relationship matters. If the teacher seeks help from his co-teachers, his burden will be lighter, and he will be learning from them, most especially since some teachers are already veterans in the academe, while most of the teachers are teaching on and off because they are still getting on board.

3. **Listen to the Students' Needs.** A maritime teacher should be approachable, not only to students, but to everyone on the campus. This is the teacher to whom students know they can go with any problems or concerns, or even to share a funny story. According to the psychologist McKeachie (1986), when the lecture begins, most students are paying attention, and for most students, that attention lasts for about 10 minutes. When there are no other activities other than lecture or discussion, it might be difficult to get a hold of the student's attention and retention. In the teaching profession, it is important to note that the students must be involved in the teaching and learning process; they must actively participate in the discussion. It is hard to discipline and maintain discipline among maritime students, so teachers have to stay strict and consistent in their rules and regulations inside the classroom.

4. **Maintain a Positive Attitude.** A good maritime teacher has his own love of learning and inspires students with his passion for education and for the course material. One of the teachers during the interview said, "I trust God", and I could see from his sincerity that he offers to God what he does and that he is happier of what he is doing than being on board and away from his family. Instructors should continuously check and assess the motivation and the trainees/students. But they should not forget themselves and the reason for the work they do.

III. Aspirations of the Informants to Improve Their Teaching Performance

1. **Pursue Professional Growth and Development.** Improving their skills and knowledge in teaching will be a great help to the academe. According to the recommendations of Section B-I/6 of the STCW Convention (which is currently non-mandatory) any person, supervisor or assessor on-board or ashore, conducting in-service training of a seafarer intended to be used in qualifying for certification, should have received: appropriate guidance in instructional techniques and assessment methods using relevant IMO Model Courses; appropriate guidance in assessment methods and practice; gained practical assessment experience under the supervision of an experienced assessor; for those individuals responsible for supervising in-service training, should have appropriate knowledge of instructional techniques, training methods and practices. The maritime teacher constantly renews himself as a professional on his quest to provide students with the highest quality of education possible.

Learning should always be a work in progress for students and teachers alike. In a nutshell, the Standards of Training, Certification and Watch-keeping (STCW) Code states that every person conducting in-service training the assessment of competence of providing training and assessment within an institution shall: have a full understanding of the specific objectives of the particular training being conducted and have knowledge and understanding of the competence to be assessed; be qualified in the tasks for which the training is to be conducted; in the instance of simulator training, every instructor shall receive appropriate guidance in instructional techniques and gain practical operational experience on the particular type of simulators used.

2. **Receive Regular Feedback on Teaching Performance.** Teachers need to know if they are doing well with what they are doing or need improvement; and the best people to validate that are the students and their co-teachers. During traditional maritime simulator training, the instructor and student interact collaboratively and continuously throughout a simulated scenario (Sellberg, 2018). To have this collaboration and interaction with the students, it is best to know where you are in terms of good teaching. The instructors, as a part of the major stakeholders of the University, are to be valued since they are the ones who provide basic knowledge in seafaring, so their improvement in the academe is a great contribution to the institution. Regular feedback helps with this improvement as much as training does because they can know what to improve and what to maintain in their teaching styles.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Conclusion

The study findings suggest that the Maritime Higher Education Institution should re-evaluate its training and seminar programs for instructors. While simulator training is important for enhancing learning and training experiences, it is crucial to also focus on teaching principles and strategies needed to effectively deliver lessons to students. By incorporating

pedagogical training into the professional development of instructors, the institution can ensure that its teaching practices align with the best practices in education.

Recommendations

Comprehensive Training Programs. Develop comprehensive training programs that address both technical skills related to simulators and teaching methodologies. This can include workshops, seminars, and courses specifically designed to enhance instructors' teaching abilities.

Pedagogical Training. Include modules or sessions on teaching principles, instructional design, classroom management, student engagement techniques, and assessment strategies. These components will equip instructors with the necessary tools and knowledge to deliver effective and engaging lessons.

Ongoing Professional Development. Offer continuous professional development opportunities for instructors, such as regular workshops or conferences focused on teaching and learning in maritime education. Encourage instructors to participate in relevant educational conferences and seminars outside the institution to stay updated with the latest teaching practices.

Peer Collaboration and Mentoring. Facilitate peer collaboration and mentoring programs where experienced instructors can share their expertise with new or less-experienced colleagues. This can create a supportive learning community among instructors, fostering the exchange of ideas and best practices.

Evaluation and Feedback. Implement a system for evaluating instructors' teaching performance and providing constructive feedback. This can be done through classroom observations, student evaluations, or self-reflection processes. Regular feedback helps instructors identify areas for improvement and promotes continuous growth.

Resources and Support. Ensure that instructors have access to adequate resources, such as teaching materials, technology, and support services. Create a supportive environment where instructors can seek assistance and guidance when needed. By revisiting their training and seminar programs to incorporate teaching principles and strategies, the Maritime Higher Education Institution can empower its instructors to become more effective educators, ultimately enhancing the learning experience for its students.

It is indeed important for the Maritime Administration to consider the possibility of exposing maritime instructors to Virtual Reality training, the same as the students are getting. They need to know more than their students.

In addition to addressing the above-mentioned concerns, conducting coping with stress seminars for maritime instructors is a beneficial initiative. Teaching can be a demanding profession, and maritime instructors face unique challenges related to the nature of their work. Providing them with the necessary tools and strategies to manage stress effectively can help enhance their well-being, job satisfaction, and overall performance.

These seminars can cover stress management techniques, self-care practices, time management skills, and strategies for maintaining a healthy work-life balance. By equipping maritime instructors with effective coping mechanisms, the Maritime Administration can contribute to their professional growth and create a supportive environment that promotes their overall well-being.

Implementing these measures demonstrates the Maritime Administration's commitment to supporting and nurturing maritime instructors, ultimately leading to improved teaching quality and student outcomes.

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Data Availability Statement

Data sharing is not applicable to this article as no new data were created or analyzed in this study; all data used were obtained from previously published sources as cited in the reference list.

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Appendices

No appendices are attached to this study.